

SURVEILLANCE CARD_ WNF_Clinical surveillance in Equidae in endemic regions

	Characteristics	Description
1	Surveillance component name	Clinical surveillance in Equidae (horses and donkeys) in endemic regions.
2	Surveillance aim	Early detection of cases.
3	Target species and group	Equidae.
4	Target sector / production type	All possible categories without distinction, including donkeys.
5	Geographical area covered	All country. (1)
6	Age group	Adults of all ages without distinction.
7	Sampling point and strategy	At horse farms. All animals showing clinical signs should be investigated (see disease brief). Special attention and incentives to monitoring and reporting can be focused on farms in areas considered of higher risk for the vector, and animals that spend most of their time outdoors.
8	Sampling time period	Year-round / not limited. (2)
9	Sampling matrix	Observation of clinical signs should lead to testing.
10	Type of disease indicators	Identification and isolation of the agent. Antibody detection.
11	Sampling unit	Individual animal whole blood sample.
12	Allocation of animal groups /animals to sampling	Adult Equidae in endemic areas.
13	Testing protocol / Diagnostic test	Identification of the agent: In-vitro and in-vivo culture Attempts to detect virus from live, clinically ill horses are not usually successful due to the fleeting viraemia. Specimens for virus isolation include brain (particularly hindbrain and medulla) and spinal cord from deceased encephalitic horses. Serological tests Antibodies can be identified in equine serum by IgM capture enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (IgM capture ELISA), haemagglutination inhibition (HI), IgG ELISA, plaque reduction neutralisation (PRN), and microtitre virus neutralisation (VN). The IgM capture ELISA

		described below is particularly useful for detecting equine antibodies resulting from recent natural exposure to WNV. In some serological assays, antibody cross-reactions with related flaviviruses, such as St Louis encephalitis virus or Japanese encephalitis virus are identified. The PRN test is the most specific among WNV serological tests; WN vaccination history must be considered in interpretation of serology results, particularly in the PRN and VN tests and IgG ELISA. (3)
14	Design prevalence (only relevant for probability-based sampling)	Not applicable; biased (non-random or non-representative) sample of the population.
15	Level of confidence (only relevant for probability-based sampling)	Not applicable; biased (non-random or non-representative) sample of the population.
16	Contribution of the component to the surveillance system	Case detection and early warning.
17	Other pathogens that could be targeted with this surveillance component	Brucella abortus, Eastern equine encephalitis (EEE), Echinococcosis, Glanders, Japanese encephalitis, Leishmaniasis, Venezuelan equine encephalitis (VEE), Western equine encephalitis (WEE).
18	References	<p>1) ECDC Culex pipiens - Factsheet for experts, last updated 15 Jun 2020</p> <p>2) TECHNICAL REPORT Field sampling methods for mosquitoes, sandflies, biting midges and ticks VectorNet project 2014–2018</p> <p>3) WOAH Terrestrial Manual Chapter 3.1.25. about West Nile fever (version adopted in May 2018)</p> <p>4) Bergmann F, Trachsel DS, Stoeckle SD, Bernis Sierra J, Lübke S, Groschup MH, Gehlen H, Ziegler U. Seroepidemiological Survey of West Nile Virus Infections in Horses from Berlin/Brandenburg and North Rhine-Westphalia, Germany. Viruses. 2022 Jan 25;14(2):243. doi: 10.3390/v14020243. PMID: 35215837; PMCID: PMC8877243.</p>
19	Additional comments	Prevalence information available 13.77% (4)

